

CREATION OF ELECTRONIC DIGITAL MAPS BASED ON GIS TECHNOLOGIES.

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Annotation.

This article provides information on the creation of electronic digital maps based on GIS technologies, the aerospace method of updating cadastral digital maps of data banks, and the technological scheme of processing photos taken from drones.

Keywords.

GIS, map, Intergraph, Leica Geosystems, PhotoMOD, Panorama, drone, space photo, data bank.

INTRODUCTION

The justification of its subject and its relevance. It is important to create, visualize electronic and digital maps based on modern GIS (geospatial systems and technologies) of socio-economic processes taking place in the world and its various regions. Also, one of the important issues is the widespread use of cartographic provision methods in the study, analysis of automated data banking. Particular attention in this regard, including in the study of agricultural, natural and socio - economic problems associated with the development of the economy in developed countries of the world, is paid to ensuring reliable information about the territory using automated data bankii electronic maps as urgent tasks of modern mapping.

World mapping focuses heavily on using modern geospatial systems and technologies in mapping various Sox, including agricultural networks, to conduct targeted scientific research focused on data visualization based on data collection, storage, analysis, processing, evaluation, and geofumadas, as well as developing

effective methods of electronic mapping. One of the important tasks in this regard, including the development of modern technologies of the geoenvironment system and cartographic provision methods in improving the method of drawing up electronic maps describing the agricultural sector, taking into account its socio-economic conditions [1-5].

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5853 of October 23, 2019 " 2020 of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan – In the decree"on approval of its strategy for the 2030s "and the decision"on measures to further improve the activities of the state committee of land resources, Geodesy, mapping and state cadastre of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated May 31, 2017 PQ-3024, this study serves to a certain extent.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

It is known that aerial photographs are used as a basis for creating cadastral digital maps of data banks, as well as cartographic materials used in 21 cadastral systems in Uzbekistan today. Photogrammetric work is carried out in an automated way when measuring phototones, which are the main sign of decoding these distance materials. The programs developed by the leading companies were widely used in the processing of the signs of optical decoding of photos.

Based on the purposeful analysis, it became known that programs such as Intergraph, Leica Geosystems, PhotoMOD, Panorama are used in the process of processing optical decoding symbols in the organizations of our republic. In order to ensure the accuracy of the work performed in these programs, space and aerial photographs taken from Landsat 7, Ikonos flying machines and uploaded to the Google system were used in the red, green, blue and near infrared spectrum zones.

The following works were carried out in the aerospace method of updating cadastral electronic digital maps of data banks:

- necessary materials for updating maps were collected, organized and the level of their use was determined;

- the changes that occurred in the area were identified;

- a technical project was developed for updating the maps.

In general, in the updating of electronic maps, aerospace materials are the main, and the rest are auxiliary data [6-10].

In the systematic research conducted for the purpose of creating digital electronic maps of data banks, it was found that the most effective method for practical solution of this issue is the GIS Panorama program. Below are the practical works carried out in this direction and their results.

Before decoding the pictures taken from space, the specialist first collects the necessary literature about the place, purposefully analyzes, organizes and evaluates the data.

Secondly, depending on the purpose and task of the work, the specialist performs space data collection. In this, the main attention is paid to the scale of generalization (generalization), spectral ranges, season and time of day of the remotely sensed materials.

Before decoding space images, they are usually enlarged several times, the objects represented in the images are compared with geographical and topographic maps, and the images with many changes are processed in special programs.

In all the literature, the assessment of changes in available information between remote sensing materials and the geographical and topographic basis is qualitatively interpreted, using the terms "more" or "less". We developed a new indicator scale that allows us to evaluate these changes with 5 levels and 100 percentiles, most importantly qualitatively and quantitatively (Table 1).

This table provides quantitative and qualitative indicators for assessing the degree of changes required to be included in the geographic and topographical frameworks [11-15].

Table 1

We used the 11th method to determine the quantitative and qualitative

Quantitative changes		Quality indicator changes	The degree of modification required to be included in geographic and topographical data
in degrees	in percentages		
1	0-20	Partially	Partial changes will be made to geographic and topographical data
2	20-40	at a low level	A low level of change is made to geographic and topographical data
3	40-60	medium level	On the basis of large-scale space materials, topocharite is processed at a moderate level
4	60-80	at a high level	On the basis of large-scale space materials, topocharite is fully processed at a high level
5	80-100	at a very high level	Special filming is done on drones and topography is fully processed

indicators in assessing the levels of changes required to be made to the geographic and topographic bases. First, in preparation for decoding the photos, a photo scheme (photomontage) of the place under investigation was created using Adobe

Photoshop. For this, images were cut to the required sizes in graphic programs, they were clarified and saved in the required formats (Fig. 1). Then a classifier was selected in the GIS panorama program depending on the scale of the topographic photo scheme (Fig. 2), the distance data was connected with the topographic trapezoid (Fig. 3) and an orthophoto plan of the place was created by transformation (Fig. 4) [16-20].

Figure 1. Cropping photos in Adobe Photoshop

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4. An orthophotoplan created based on the photos taken.

Decryption is the most complicated process when updating maps. For this, it is necessary to evaluate the indicators of the levels of changes required to be included in the geographical and topographical bases in terms of quantity and quality.

The most appropriate and effective way to quantitatively and qualitatively assess indicators of change levels that have occurred over time is the use of remote sensing data. This task is based on the Adobe Photoshop program, the changes in space are determined by the stereophotogrammetric method and are evaluated based on the newly developed scale [21-25].

The principles of decoding when updating maps are carried out depending on the changes in the levels of change required to be included in the geographic and topographic bases in terms of quantity (Table 1, columns 1 and 2) and quality (Table 1, columns 1 and 2).

If the change index is very high, i.e. 5 points (or 80%) and above, all the objects of the research area require re-surveying with the help of drones. will be re-decoded and the obtained results will be completely reduced to the topographical basis.

If the change indicators are at a high level of 4 points (or 60-80%), it is not necessary to take a new survey with the help of drones. In this case, it is considered sufficient to fully decipher large-scale space materials and reduce the results obtained from them to a topographical basis.

If the indicators of change are 3 points in the middle (or 40-60%), in this case, the changes recorded in large-scale space materials and the obtained results are reset to the topographic basis.

If the indicators of change are low, that is, 2 points (or 20-40%), in this case, low-level changes determined from space photographs are made to geographic and topographical data.

If the indicators of change are partial at 1 point (or 20%) and below, it is limited to include in the topographic basis only the results of very small changes detected during the re-decoding process of the place being searched [26-30].

Thus, if necessary, the obtained distance photographs are combined and an orthophotoplan is prepared according to the nomenclature of the place at the required scale, the new objects identified on the basis of the orthophotoplan and stereopairs are included in the geographical and topographic bases according to the indicators of the degree of change, and they are organized according to each object, basics are stored in separate layers.

Above, we presented in general the principles of determining and evaluating the change levels of new objects, determined mainly by means of remote sensing materials, in terms of quantity and quality indicators, and the technology of including them in geographical and topographic bases. Another complex task in this methodology is the issue of vector mapping of all, including new, objects in the photos. We used the "Editor card" panel to solve this problem. In this case, the "Create object" action is activated, and then the "Vybor object" window opens. In this window, the numbered object type, style (linear, polygonal, dotted), layer

name is given, and the objects are numbered. When all objects are named and numbered in separate layers, the program automatically opens the "Semantics" window. After all objects are digitized in this sequence, the raster image is deleted.

Figure 5. View of the digital topographic map in the Panorama program.

Then the digital map created in the GIS Panorama program was exported to the map of data banks.

It is known that today the use of drones is being widely implemented in the remote survey of the earth and in the detection and evaluation of changes related to new objects. Although the use of such tools increases work productivity, it requires some economic output. Therefore, when planning drone surveying, first of all, select small areas only in areas with extremely high change indicators, i.e., 5 points (or 80%) and above. we consider the use of technology to be the most appropriate choice [31-34].

We have developed a special technology to detect new objects and assess the levels of change indicators in the area by means of photographs taken from unmanned aerial vehicles Figure 6.

Figure 6. Technological scheme of processing photos taken from unmanned aerial vehicles

In the process of filming with the help of drone devices, the specialist directly goes to the work area, determines the direction of the flight device and programs it.

Drone footage speeds up the workflow and costs less than aerial and space photography. Remote sensing data is processed automatically in the Agisoft Photoscan program in the following sequence:

- photos are initially uploaded to the program;
- tabular data on photo coordinates is loaded;
- photos are placed in trapezoids according to coordinates;
- a point model of the earth's surface is created;
- if there are geodetic networks in the place, photographs and orthophotoplans are connected to it;
- the model is optimized and regulated;
- orthophotoplane height matrices are exported.

To perform this operation, the memory settings of the computer must be at a high level.

Figure 7. Uploading the captured photos to the Agisoft PhotoScan program

Figure 8. Select the necessary coordinates.

The set of obtained results allows creating a 2- and 3-dimensional model of the area.

Figure 9

Figure 10

The effect of the atmospheric factor is important in the formation of images in photos taken by drones, because there is no shadow of objects in cloudy weather, and the possibility of observing them in volume is high.

In addition, each of the photos taken by drones will have its own precise coordinate system based on the GPS system built into the device. Photos are placed on the grid created according to these coordinates, and the boundaries of the contours of the objects in the photo are visualized (Figures 9-10).

In this method of creating a digital map of data banks, the necessary concepts about how to update topographic maps are given.

Thus, the method of comparison is important when creating a digital map of data banks. In this process, a photo of new objects is placed under the existing map, and then the objects on the topo map and the photo are compared.

If the change indicators are partial or low in the research area, these changes are reduced to the old topography.

If the rate of change is medium or high, the topochart is re-numbered.

If the rate of change is extremely high, 5 points (or 80%) and above, all the objects of the research area will be photographed again with the help of drones, and the photos taken will be completely re-decoded and it is recommended to fully download the obtained results to topographic basis.

CONCLUSION

Projects related to the creation of a unified state cadastre in the development of cadastral map programs of data banks and, first of all, were carried out in

connection with the cartographic systems of the land cadastre and buildings and structures cadastre, and the maintenance of the cadastre was carried out by developing an algorithm for their cartographic support released

In the development of the algorithm for maintaining the cadastre of data banks and creating maps, the main attention was focused on cartographic models and the system of data banks, and a three-level interdependent system was created.

The initial set of maps serves as the basis for the creation of the base series of the cadastre of data banks. In this process, at first, the information system of the cadastre of regional departments' lower level, i.e., district-level data banks is formed. Then we recommend the production of special maps for the differentiation, study and evaluation of data banks for regional departments at the middle - regional level and high level - at the republican level.

When updating the cadastral maps of data banks, the indicators of the required levels of changes were evaluated quantitatively and qualitatively, using aero-space photos, a five-level scale of qualitative and quantitative indicators of changes was developed. Based on this developed 5-point scale, we suggest updating cadastral maps of data banks.

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